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XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK ROLINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli va ahamiyati yoritilgan. Xususiy tadbirkorlik yangi ish o‘rinlarini yaratish, raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish, innovatsiyalarni joriy etish va mahalliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish orqali xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasiga qanday ta‘sir ko‘rsatishi tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish yo‘llari, jumladan huquqiy baza, moliyaviy qo‘llab-quvvatlash, kadrlar malakasini oshirish va raqamli iqtisodiyot imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish kabi yo‘nalishlar muhokama etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Xususiy tadbirkorlik, xizmat ko‘rsatish, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, raqobatbardoshlik, innovatsiyalar, moliyaviy qo‘llab-quvvatlash, raqamli iqtisodiyot, davlat-xususiy sheriklik.

Kirish. Xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasining mamlakat iqtisodiyoti va ijtimoiy hayotida o‘rni ortib borayotgani bois, bu sohada xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bozor iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishi jarayonida tadbirkorlik faoliyati iqtisodiy faollikni oshirish, yangi ish o‘rinlarini yaratish va aholi farovonligini ta‘minlashda asosiy vositalardan biriga aylanmoqda. Shu sababli xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish uchun xususiy tadbirkorlikni yanada rag‘batlantirish va uning rolini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

O‘zbekiston sharoitida ushbu sektor iqtisodiy o‘rni rag‘batlantirish, aholi bandligini ta‘minlash va turmush darajasini oshirishning asosiy omillaridan biri sifatida ko‘riladi. Shu munosabat bilan xizmat ko‘rsatish korxonalarida kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish masalalari katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Asosiy qism. Xususiy tadbirkorlik xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasida bir qator afzalliklarga ega bo‘lib, ushbu tarmoqda iqtisodiy faollikni oshiradi va xizmatlar sifatini yaxshilashda muhim rol

o'ynaydi. Xususiy tadbirkorlik orqali ko'plab yangi korxonalar tashkil qilinib, ularning bozorga kirishi raqobatni kuchaytiradi, bu esa sifatli xizmatlarni arzon narxlarda taklif etish imkoniyatini yaratadi. Bundan tashqari, tadbirkorlar bozor ehtiyojlariga mos xizmat turlarini joriy qilib, innovatsiyalarni tezroq tatbiq etadilar.

Xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xizmat ko'rsatish sohasidagi ahamiyati

1. Xususiy tadbirkorlik xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ayniqsa, kichik va o'rta tadbirkorlik subyektlari aholini ish bilan ta'minlashda katta rol o'ynaydi. Bu esa mehnat bozorida muammolarni kamaytiradi va aholi bandligini oshiradi.

2. Xususiy tadbirkorlar raqobat muhitini yaratishda muhim rol o'ynaydilar. Ular bozorga yangi g'oyalar va innovatsion texnologiyalarni olib kirish orqali xizmatlar sifatini yaxshilaydi va narxlarni pasaytiradi. Natijada, iste'molchilar sifatli xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniga ega bo'ladilar.

3. Xususiy tadbirkorlar o'z faoliyati orqali mahalliy bozorlarni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Ular mahalliy resurslarni samarali ishlatib, daromadlarni ichki iqtisodiy muomalaga jalb qiladi, bu esa o'z navbatida, iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantiradi.

4. Xususiy tadbirkorlik xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy qilish imkoniyatlarini oshiradi. Elektron tijorat, onlayn xizmatlar, raqamli platformalar va zamonaviy IT texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali xizmat ko'rsatish sifati va samaradorligi oshadi. Tadbirkorlar raqamli innovatsiyalarni tezroq joriy qilib, iste'molchilarga yanada qulay va samarali xizmatlarni taklif qilish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda bir qator strategik chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilishi zarur. Bu esa xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining o'sishini jadallashtirib, iqtisodiy faollikni kuchaytirishga yordam beradi. Quyida ushbu yo'nalishdagi asosiy yo'llar ko'rib chiqiladi:

1. Huquqiy baza va tartibotni soddalashtirish. Xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish uchun davlat tomonidan qulay huquqiy baza yaratish va tartibotni soddalashtirish zarur. Bu borada litsenziyalash va ruxsatnoma olish jarayonlarini yengillashtirish, soliqlarni kamaytirish va tadbirkorlik faoliyatini boshlash uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

2. Moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash. Xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyaviy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari samaradorligini oshirish zarur. Bunda tijorat banklari tomonidan kichik va o'rta biznes subyektlariga uzoq muddatli kreditlar ajratish, davlat tomonidan subsidiya va grantlarni taqdim etish hamda investitsion imkoniyatlarni kengaytirish muhim rol o'ynaydi.

3. Ta'lim va malaka oshirish. Xususiy tadbirkorlik sohasida muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanish uchun kadrlar tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish dasturlarini amalga oshirish muhimdir. Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida ishlaydigan xodimlarning zamonaviy bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishi, tadbirkorlarning biznes boshqaruvi sohasida bilimlarini oshirish iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishga yordam beradi.

4. Davlat-xususiy sheriklik. Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik tizimini rivojlantirish orqali xususiy tadbirkorlikni rag'batlantirish mumkin. Davlat va xususiy

sektor o'rtasidagi hamkorlik infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishda, ijtimoiy xizmatlarni ko'rsatishda va yangi bozorlarni rivojlantirishda katta rol o'ynaydi.

5. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish. Xususiy tadbirkorlikning raqamli iqtisodiyot imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishi xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida o'sishni ta'minlaydi. Raqamli platformalar orqali marketing, elektron tijorat va mijozlar bilan munosabatlarni samarali boshqarish imkoniyatlari yaratadi. Bu esa biznesni global bozorga olib chiqish imkoniyatini oshiradi.

Xulosa. Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda xususiy tadbirkorlikning o'rni va roli juda katta. Xususiy sektorning faol ishtiroki iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish, raqobatni oshirish va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni tatbiq etishda hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Shuning uchun davlat va jamoatchilik tomonidan xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish yo'nalishida ko'rsatiladigan qo'llab-quvvatlash chora-tadbirlari yanada samarali bo'lishi kerak. Innovatsion yondashuvlar va raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida xususiy tadbirkorlarning roli va ta'siri ortib borishi mamlakat iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi.

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